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“Druggability and Genetic Variability of the ADP-bound Pocket of SARS-CoV-2 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase NiRAN domain Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

The RNA-dependent RNA-polymerase (RdRp) also known as non-structural protein 12 (nsp12) is the target of antiviral agent remdesivir. Nsp12 has an important role in viral genome replication and transcription. (Chen et al., 2020)

Chen et al. identified a new pocket on the N-terminal extension of nsp12 occupied by ADP-Mg²⁺ after solving the structure of the helicase-polymerase complex. This ADP-bound pocket is on the N-terminal nidovirus RdRp-associated nucleotidyltransferase (NiRAN) domain which is also well-resolved. (Chen et al., 2020).

Based on conservation profile across nidovirales (an order of positive-stranded RNA viruses including SARS-CoV-2), the NiRAN domain is believed to have nucleotidyltransferase activity, though the protein substrates to which nucleotides are added by the NiRAN domain are unknown. Reverse genetics was used to establish the importance of NiRAN domain for nidoviral replication: mutating residues conserved in NiRAN domains induces significant reduction of SARS-CoV-1 and Equine viral arteritis (EAV) viral titers in cell culture (Lehmann et al., 2015). Previous structural homology search of SARS-CoV-1 nsp12 NiRAN domain showed significant homology with protein kinases, including some key catalytic residues such as Asn209 and NiRAN conserved residues As218 and Phe219. (Kirchdoerfer et al., 2019)

For our project, we were interested in assessing the druggability of this pocket and finding out how conserved is this site both across past and novel coronaviruses and across SARS-CoV-2 samples from COVID-19 patients.

To achieve our first aim, we used a tool called sitemap (Schrodinger, NY) to assess the druggability of the ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp using the available nsp12 structure in the protein data bank (PDB code: 6xez). The result indicates that this highly polar pocket is a difficult druggable site (Dscore = 0.85) as shown in figure 1. (Halgren, 2009)

Figure 1. Druggability assessment of the ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp.

In figure 2, I highlight the thirty amino acid residues that line this site of interest as identified by their proximity ($\sim 2.8\text{\AA}$) to both the bound ADP molecule and the Van der Waals boundaries of the corresponding pocket mapped by ICM. (Molsoft, San Diego). The list of residues includes: R33, A34, F35, D36, I37, Y38, K50, N52, R55, V71, K73, H75, N79, R116, L119, T123, A125, D126, V204, T206, D208, N209, Y217, D218, G220, D221, F222, S236, Y728, R733.

Figure 2. The 30 amino acid sidechains surrounding ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp.

As part of our second aim, we conducted a broad survey of viral proteins from Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. By integrating variability and druggability data we can infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum viral inhibitors against coronaviruses. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses circulating in bat reservoir species.

To assess this site's genetic variability, we first looked at 27 reviewed sequences from Uniprot, of which 6 are from the Alphacoronavirus genus and 21 from the Betacoronavirus genus. In figure 3, the diversity dendrogram shows the two clusters of Alphacoronavirus and Betacoronavirus organisms. The letters of varying sizes show the profile of residues at each specific amino acid position.

We observe that 21 out of 30 residues are identical at this site which translates into 70% identity as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3. The diversity dendrogram of ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp for the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera.

For better visualization of the variations identified among the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus, we mapped the variations onto the crystal structure of nsp12 as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Mapping the genetic variation of UniProt entries belonging to Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera onto SARS-CoV-2 RdRp Crystal structure (PDB: 6xez). The nine non-conserved residues among the entries of both Alpha- and Betacoronavirus include I37, Y38, V71, H75, N79, A125, V204, F222, S236 as shown in sticks representation on the right panel.

If we only look across the 21 Betacoronavirus sequences (the genus of SARS-CoV-2 virus), we see a 73% conservation of residues at the ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp.

Figure 5. The diversity dendrogram of ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp for the entries of Betacoronavirus genus.

To complete our second aim and as a follow-up to assessing the genetic variability among Alphacoronavirus and Betacoronavirus entries, we also looked at the conservation of this site across SARS-CoV-2 samples. Our collaborator, Nicola De Maio, from Nick Goldman’s lab at the European Bioinformatics Institute has identified the non-synonymous mutations at ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp across more than 39000 SARS-CoV-2 samples. Altogether he

identified non-synonymous mutations at 6 unique amino acid residues consisting of 6 unique non-synonymous variants. In table 1, there are details about the mutation events underlying these variants.

index	Wild type amino acid in SARS-CoV-2	Non-synonymous variants		Codon one	Codon two	Codon three	Source of the Variants
1	Y38	Y (39261)		t (39264) c (10)	a (39274)	c (39263) t (8)	8 synonymous variants from Switzerland, USA, England. 10 H variants England (Bristol).
		1	H (10)				
2	H75	H (39329)		c (39334)	a (39335)	a (4), c (39201) t (130)	4 Q variants from USA. 130 synonymous variants from USA (most of them), Luxembourg, England, Australia, Chile, Thailand, Uruguay.
		2	Q (4)				
3	A125	A (39338)		g (39339) t (1)	c (39341)	a (39335) c (4)	1 S variant from England EPI_ISL_470198. 4 Synonymous variants from USA
		3	S (1)				
4	F222	F (39334)		t (39334) c (7)	c (15874)	a (15874)	7 L variants from the USA.
		4	L (7)				
5	S236	S (39340)		t (39340) g (1)	c (39341)	t (39339) c (2)	1 A variant from England EPI_ISL_470432. 2 synonymous variants from the Netherlands and Taiwan.
		5	A (1)				
6	R733	R (39341)		a (39342)	g (39341) a (1)	a (39342)	1 K variant from the USA, EPI_ISL_434888.
		6	K (1)				

Table 1. Non-synonymous Variants at ADP-bound pocket of NiRAN domain of RdRp across more than 39000 SARS-CoV-2 samples. (Nicola De Maio, 2020). The source of the variants is highlighted in bold font.

Figure 6. Mapping the SARS-CoV-2 non-synonymous variants positions onto SARS-CoV-2 RdRp Crystal structure (PDB: 6xez). The non-synonymous variants positions include: Y38, H75, A125, F222, S236, R733.

While we have computationally evaluated the effect of mutations on ligand binding for other binding pockets found in SARS-CoV-2 protein structures, we believe the ADP site of the RdRp NiRAN domain is not well suited for this type of exercise. First, as can be seen Fig.2, ADP exploits only a portion of the pocket, the interaction seems to be mainly driven by the phosphate moiety of the ligand and putative inhibitors targeting this site would presumably not mimic the ADP-RdRp interactions. Second, the 3.5 Å resolution of this structure is not within the resolution range that is typically required for reliable computational modeling.

Comparison with previously analyzed RdRp pockets:

We previously analyzed the druggability and conservation of the catalytic site and an ectopic site (that we called M666 pocket) of RdRp. We find that the and ectopic pocket (Dscore = 1.03) is more druggable than the catalytic pocket (Dscore 0.86) occupied by RNA-conjugated Rmedesivir and the NiRAN pocket (Dscore=0.85).

On the other end, the catalytic site of RdRp is among the most conserved pockets that we have seen across SARS-CoV-2 protein structures (83% conserved in coronaviruses) followed by the NiRAN pocket (70% conserved) and the M666 pocket (33% conserved).

We observe a related trend when looking at mutation rates across COVID-19 samples: the catalytic site and NiRAN pocket were genetically more stable, with 6 unique mutations found in 6 samples each, while the M666 pocket was more prone to mutations (10 mutations found in 13 variants).

A strategy may be to develop compounds that include a chelating moiety to engage the Mg²⁺ observed in the ADP-bound NiRAN pocket. This site has reasonable genetic stability and is potentially an interesting target for the development of broad-spectrum inhibitors.

References

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